

IMPROVING THE PROCEDURE FOR CONDUCTING INFORMATION AND ANALYTICAL ACTIVITIES IN INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES IS A CURRENT DEMAND OF OUR TIME

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Abstract: This article examines the issues of improving the procedure for conducting information and analytical activities in internal affairs bodies. Today, the rapid development of modern technologies and information systems, as well as the changes occurring in society, necessitate organizing activities in this field based on new approaches. The article analyzes existing problems in information-analytical processes and develops proposals for increasing their effectiveness. Additionally, the possibilities of studying foreign experiences and adapting them to local conditions are discussed. This research is of great importance in optimizing the activities of internal affairs bodies and ensuring public safety, meeting the demands of our time.

Keywords: Concepts in the process of information and analytical activity in internal affairs bodies: information, analysis, forecasting, activity, types of analysis and their role in the activities of internal affairs are described

In order to enhance digital skills in public administration, it is necessary, first and foremost, to develop and continuously improve the mechanism for advancing civil servants' skills and qualifications in the field of information and communication technologies.[1]

Sh.M. Mirziyoyev

The effectiveness of management activities in internal affairs bodies largely depends on the completeness, reliability, and relevance of obtaining and disseminating information necessary for making informed decisions on issues affecting the legal and legitimate interests of the population. In our country, in the areas of combating crime, preventing offenses, and ensuring public safety, internal affairs bodies must organize systematic work to ensure citizens' freedom, their right to appeal and receive relevant information, and establish cooperation between state bodies and the population. In turn, the realization of citizens' right to receive information depends on the effective organization, maintenance, and development of bilateral relations between internal affairs bodies and the population. Such functions of internal affairs bodies can be performed by the information service. The main goal of carrying out information and analytical activities in internal affairs bodies is to create a foundation for the effective use of internal affairs resources in fighting crime, preventing offenses, and ensuring public safety.

A system is a collection of interconnected and interacting elements and parts that form a single whole.

Structure is the organization of a system, manifested in its division into constituent parts, ensuring its integrity, functioning, and movement, with mutually determined placement and connections between them.

Task - one of the roles performed by the system and its elements or constituent parts; the designation of the system and its parts; types of system activity.

Goal - the object of aspiration, a pre-planned final idea, the expected result of the system's actions, determining why the system operates. [2]

Information support is a set of methods and tools for encoding, storing, and organizing information, including standardized documentation systems for creating databases in information systems.

The reliability and quality of management decisions made in internal affairs bodies largely depend on the quality of the developed information support. For information to be of high quality, we need to choose its sources correctly.

Software is a set of software tools for creating and using a data processing system using computer technology. Software includes basic (general system) and applied (special) software products.

Basic software tools serve to automate human-computer interaction, data processing, organization of standard procedures, and monitoring and diagnostics of technical tools' operation.

Application software represents a set of software products designed to automate the solution of functional tasks in information systems. They can be developed as universal tools (text editors, spreadsheets, database management systems) and special tools - various objects implementing functional subsystems (economic, engineering, technical, etc.).

Technical support is a complex of technical means used for the functioning of a data processing system. This software includes devices that process data and perform standard operations. Such devices include, in addition to computers, peripheral technical means, various organizational equipment, telecommunications, and communication tools.

Legal support represents a set of legal norms regulating the creation and functioning of the information system.

Linguistic provisioning consists of a set of language tools used at different stages of creating and using MQIT to enhance the effectiveness of human-computer communication development and provision.[3]

Information should also be comprehensively and fully provided in the internal affairs bodies.

Information and analytical activities in the internal affairs bodies are carried out by information and analytical assistants to the heads of the Information and Analytical Department and information and analytical departments (divisions) of structural subdivisions of the Organizational Department of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the Main Department of Internal Affairs of the city of Tashkent and Tashkent region, regional inspectorates and information and analytical departments, and district (city) departments (divisions) of internal affairs.

In all internal affairs bodies, Information and Analytical Units, within their competence, ensure and implement the tasks of systematic analysis, assessment, and development of comprehensive measures for the operational service of internal affairs bodies in the field of combating crime, preventing offenses, managing and controlling activities to ensure public safety.

Employees carrying out information and analytical work in internal affairs bodies must mainly collect, systematize, analyze, and summarize information and analytical activity data. In this regard, the following will be carried out:

- Identify data sources; Identifying the sources of information about events, incidents, and crimes, and collecting information.

- determines the procedure for compiling and submitting a list of information and analytical data; compiles a list of sources from which to obtain the necessary information and takes measures to obtain it.

- establishing contacts with the relevant bodies of state administration and citizens' self-government, as well as public organizations for the purpose of data collection; Collects data based on requests from other state and public organizations to obtain relevant information from targeted information sources.

- assessment of the significance, completeness, and reliability of the incoming information; Each received data is first studied, analyzed, and after verification of reliability, the information is entered into the data.

- systematization of information by content, direction, and relevance; Each obtained data is summarized based on the corresponding systematization, distributed according to content and direction.

- formation of a database. In each department, depending on the content and directions of the information received, a special database is created and information is collected.

In the effective use of force by internal affairs bodies and the prevention of crime and offenses, as well as ensuring public safety, it is necessary to collect and analyze information through intelligence activities. This includes data on the criminogenic situation, external factors influencing the operational and service activities of law enforcement agencies and internal affairs bodies, as well as information on the forces and resources of internal affairs bodies and the results of their operational and service activities. In modern conditions, information services should perform the function of public relations consulting. Moreover, having the ability to obtain and analyze complete information, the information service can become an essential advisor to the khokim in improving his relationships both with his departments and with the population. Therefore, the term "khokimiyat information service" carries a broad meaning. Information service employees must not only be good psychologists and analysts but also have a deep understanding and ability to analyze the country's domestic and foreign policy, as well as the main directions of the khokimiyat's activities. In the event of an unpleasant or uncomfortable situation, the information service should immediately respond and be able to transform conflict situations into constructive cooperation by presenting information correctly. We also agree with the definition of information service given by these scholars.

An information system is an interconnected set of methods, tools, and individuals used to collect, store, process, and transmit information to achieve a specific goal.

Information systems have existed since the emergence of society, as at different stages of development, society has required systematized, pre-prepared information for its management. This especially applies to production processes - those related to the production of tangible and intangible goods. These are vitally important for the development of society. Production processes, in particular, are rapidly improving. As they develop, management

becomes more complex, which, in turn, stimulates the improvement and development of information systems.

In the process of continuous analysis of the crime situation in the internal affairs bodies, data collection in service areas is carried out in the following processes:

- statistical data on the socio-economic, demographic, and criminogenic situation in the service area; This includes statistical data on all industrial enterprises located in the region, living conditions of the population, population size, the number of men and women, nationality, employment, the state of crime, and factors influencing it.

- information on the forces and resources of internal affairs bodies, the results of operational-search activities, the state of discipline and compliance with legislation; - information on the number of personnel in internal affairs bodies, technical means, data, professional skills, the results of operational-search activities, i.e., statistical reporting, information on cases of violation of law and service discipline by personnel.

- information and analytical data of internal affairs and other law enforcement agencies; information exchange and data collection with information services of internal affairs bodies, information services of the Prosecutor's Office, Customs, State Security and judicial bodies:

- information on judicial and legal practice; Information on the continuous analysis of the results of work in the fight against crime by judicial bodies, obtained from information services.

- certificates of inspection and control of the activities of internal affairs bodies; The Ministry and territorial bodies of internal affairs enter data from the analysis of information on the results of comprehensive and control inspections of the activities of lower-level internal affairs bodies and the implementation of the established measures.

- scientific research conducted on the criminogenic situation and the fight against crime, information on the attitude of the population to the activities of internal affairs bodies; methodological manuals created jointly with scientific workers on the criminogenic situation and the fight against crime conducted in the territories of internal affairs bodies, information on the results of surveys conducted among the population - appeals of individuals and legal entities; Daily appeals from individuals and legal entities to internal affairs bodies are received in various forms, and each appeal is monitored by managers, implementation is ensured, and monthly reports are maintained and analyzed, data is compiled.

- reports and articles in local and foreign mass media, as well as information on the Internet about the activities of internal affairs bodies.

It should be noted that the information and analytical activity

there are international independent structures that prepare relevant analytical information not only on the basis of state orders, but also on the basis of orders from private sector representatives.

Such independent structures are called "think tanks."

is called. Examples of international think tanks include the RAND Corporation, the Club of Rome, the Brookings Institution, Chatham House (Great Britain), the Carnegie Foundation, Transparency International, and others.

Also, according to the experience of many countries, information and analytical the presence of a structure carrying out activities in state bodies and organizations is the basis for ensuring an objective consideration of problems in this area.

In this case, the information-analytical structure is tasked with constantly monitoring changes in the field and predicting possible problematic situations and proposing solutions. The above information is also reflected in the information-analytical work of the internal affairs bodies.

Scientific information systems are designed to automate the activities of researchers, analyze statistical information, and manage experiments. Scientific information systems are designed to automate the activities of researchers, analyze statistical information, and manage experiments. In a globalized information space, it is impossible to completely limit or control the means of psycho-informational influence. Democratic governance and the diversity of opinions do not allow this. In fact, every piece of information disseminated must be repeatedly verified. But reality does not allow this mirage to be realized. Therefore, it is better to look for other solutions to the problem.

Firstly, it is necessary to form an attitude towards external threats. Secondly, it is necessary to improve the knowledge and analytical skills of citizens. So that they themselves have the opportunity to distinguish white from black. Thirdly, in the information flow, bring information that meets the interests of society and the state to a level that people can quickly perceive and believe. If this task is sufficiently implemented, the impact of negative information on public consciousness will sharply decrease. Fourthly, increasing trust in national media. Because the most important conditions for ensuring information security are related to the issue of eliminating information shortages in society. If the population does not trust local media and does not accept them as the main source of information, it is natural for them to look for other sources. Fifthly, providing the field of information management and technologies with qualified personnel. The strengthening of the integration of developing countries into the international community requires them to create their own image in the global information space. Because no matter how intense globalization makes human life, it seriously threatens the identity of each nation, its loyalty to national values and traditions, and, in general, its preservation as a nation. Therefore, the problems of ensuring information security are of great importance today not only in developing countries, but also in the leading countries of the world. In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Principles and Guarantees of Freedom of Information," "the sphere of activity of entities related to the creation, processing, and use of information is the information sphere," and "information protection is measures to prevent threats to information security and eliminate their consequences." "prevention of threats to the security of the individual, society, and the state in the information sphere; Also, "any information, if its illegal handling may cause harm to the owner, possessor, user of information and other persons, must be protected," that is, ensuring the security of such information is established by law, and the protection of information is carried out for the following purposes: ensuring the confidentiality of information, preventing its dissemination, theft, and loss; preventing the distortion and falsification of information.

Therefore, in 2007, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan in Connection with Strengthening Responsibility for Committing Unlawful Actions in the Field of Informatization and Data Transmission" was adopted.

It is important to ensure the information security of society and the state. "The information security of society is achieved through: developing the foundations of a

democratic civil society, ensuring freedom of mass media; preventing unlawful psychological influence on public consciousness through information and its misleading; preserving and developing the spiritual, cultural, and historical wealth of society, as well as the country's scientific and technical potential; creating a system to counter information expansion aimed at undermining national identity, alienating society from historical and national traditions and customs, destabilizing the socio-political situation, and disrupting interethnic and interfaith harmony."The information security of the state is ensured by: implementing economic, political, organizational, and other measures to counter threats to security in the information sphere; protecting state secrets and state information resources from unauthorized access; integrating the Republic of Uzbekistan into the global information space and modern telecommunications systems; protecting against the dissemination of information that includes open calls for the violent overthrow of the constitutional order, violation of territorial integrity and sovereignty, seizure of power or removal of legally elected or appointed government representatives, and other encroachments on the state system; countering the spread of information that promotes war and violence, cruelty, incites social, national, racial and religious enmity, and propagates ideas of terrorism and religious extremism." Ensuring information security in internal affairs bodies is the main task of every analyst. Improving information and analytical activities in internal affairs bodies and training qualified personnel in this area is a pressing task today.

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